

Short name	Marine and land use planning	Long name	Economic implications of complex marine and land-use planning processes
Geographical scope	All		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>Marine and land-use planning can support or hinder deployment of CCS, depending how they are done. The lack of experience with CO₂-storage sites and related infrastructure causes severe uncertainties, which affects the economic viability and attractiveness. Planning policies are determined at the member state, region or more local level and determine what can be built where. Development planning can include a spatial determination of which developments are suitable for which locations, and/or policies to enable planners to decide applications for new developments or change or use / alterations to existing developments. Plans and planning policies can take many years to put in place, and may not be designed to deal with new classes of development such as CCS and hydrogen infrastructure. All of this risks causing excessive barriers to entry and thus can have a deterrent effect on financing.</p> <p>Issues that need to be addressed in spatial planning include how to deal with the potential for competing uses of the sea and seabed, such as for offshore wind, fishing, leisure, nature conservation etc. Competing use-cases for the same surfaces thus can raise the economic threshold for CCUS viability.</p> <p>Onshore, there may be the need for planning authorities to work together on cross-border infrastructure projects. Complex planning applications can take years and can threaten economic viability if this is not factored in at an early stage.</p> <p>Planning is often associated and has interrelationships with environmental and health and safety consenting and permitting. There is likely to be a need for training and capacity building for planners and regulators to know how to deal with new developments including CO₂ capture, and pipeline transport; and lack of capacity and knowledge can delay the process.</p> <p>Excessive planning durations could lead to partners giving up early, thus challenging previously established business cases (as projections of cost and revenues change).</p>		
Key examples where this issue	The UK's Energy Integration Project ¹ explores how different offshore energy systems (oil and gas, renewables, hydrogen and carbon capture and storage) could be co-ordinated across the UK Continental Shelf		

¹ <https://www.nstauthority.co.uk/the-move-to-net-zero/energy-integration/>

manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<p>(UKCS) for environmental and efficiency gains, including identifying technical, regulatory and economic hurdles.</p> <p>In 2001 the Scottish Government and partners carried out a regulatory test exercise to understand the many processes and permits required to develop a CCS project; based on this, Scottish Carbon Capture & Storage developed a <i>CCS Regulatory Toolkit</i>². A review of the regulations around CCS in Scotland has since been updated, but has not been published.</p>
Other issues this affects	<p>Permitting processes, complexity of value-chains, business models,</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The National Subsea Research Initiative (NSRI); (n.d.): Energy Integration, https://www.nstauthority.co.uk/the-move-to-net-zero/energy-integration/, United Kingdom. • Scottish Carbon Capture and Storage (SCCS); (2016): CCS Toolkit, https://www.sccs.org.uk/images/expertise/reports/toolkit/CCS-Toolkit-Full.pdf, United Kingdom.

² <https://www.sccs.org.uk/images/expertise/reports/toolkit/CCS-Toolkit-Full.pdf>